

The Influence of Macroeconomic Variables: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract: This study aims to determine the development of research around the influence of Macroeconomic variables. The research was conducted from 1997 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sprott, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Macroeconomics". Based on the search results, there were 441 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to influence of Macroeconomic variables is divided into 5 clusters and 139 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a Library Research study, there are 2 main themes related to the influence of Macroeconomic variables.

Keywords: Macroeconomics; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research

Introduction

The economy is a system that regulates how the resources available in a country, such as labor, capital and raw materials, are used to meet human needs and desires. The economy is an important factor for the survival of a country because a healthy economy can improve people's welfare, create jobs, and strengthen political stability and security of a country. Apart from that, the economy can also influence the growth and development of a country, as well as help that country to compete in the global arena. Economics also has other roles, namely as a measure of economic growth, measuring inflation, measuring a country's unemployment rate, helping to understand and manage international trade, and helping to manage public policy. The economy is the pulse point of a country, this is the basis for a country to be said to be a developed country if its economic growth is good, technology is developing and infrastructure is well developed, so that it can support economic growth and progress (Priyono & Candra, 2016).

Economics is the study of how individuals and societies make choices regarding the use of available resources, such as natural resources, capital, and people. In economics, we learn about how people make decisions with various associated consequences. Individual decisions are combined become the people's choice. Economics is also a behavioral science or social science that discusses how individuals, companies, or society fulfill their needs through various available choices, such as primary, secondary, and tertiary needs. Companies also have to make choices about what goods to produce, to whom to distribute the production results, or what goods will be consumed by society. These various problems are related to how to fulfill, produce and distribute goods and services, whether these goods are economic goods or public goods. Economics also deals with economic systems, such as market systems or socialist systems, and how they interact with factors such as prices, income, and consumption. Apart from that, economics also discusses how the government can influence the economy by using tools such as taxes, subsidies and regulations (Zahara & Anwar, 2020). Economics is also divided into two, namely macro and micro economics.

Economic progress is also greatly influenced by the economic crisis. Macroeconomic variables are one of the factors used to measure and analyze the overall economic condition of a country. This variable also includes various economic aspects that can explain and describe economic performance and changes that occur over a certain period of time. This research is in line with (Yasmin & Muharam, 2021) macroeconomic variables are one of the external factors that can influence financial distress conditions. Indicators that can be measured from macroeconomic factors, namely the value of exchange rate sensitivity and inflation sensitivity) in other research, macroeconomics greatly influences a country's economy. This is in accordance with research (Putra, 2021) that macro variables are ones that can influence the IHSG value.

Scientific publications regarding macroeconomics also continue to increase from year to year based on searches via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Even in 2022, there will be 40 studies related to macroeconomics. This shows that the development of macroeconomic research is very rapid. The aim of this research is to determine a map of the development of research regarding economic activities, especially macroeconomics in Indonesia over a period of 40 years. This shows that the development of macroeconomic research is very rapid. Researchers provide a fairly long time span, hoping that the data obtained will be more valid and accurate. In this study, data were processed using: (1) Bibliometric studies, the VOSviewer bibliometric method was used to analyze and study maps of literature development a scientific field, especially scientific publications; and (2) Library Research studies are used to examine, recognize and review articles from accredited national journals, Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research can explain all research topics regarding macroeconomics. This can be a reference for researchers in areas of research gaps that are rarely researched. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding Microeconomics in Indonesia which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can be used as references for future researchers.

Literature Review

Macroeconomics is a science that analyzes the overall state of economic activities. In macro, we no longer discuss the activities carried out by producers, consumers or owners of production factors, but discuss more broadly the overall actions of economic actors, namely consumers, entrepreneurs, government, financial institutions and other countries and how these actions influence movements. to the economy as a whole. In a more specific sense, macroeconomics studies total variables such as national income, consumption, public savings, total investment, etc. (Yasmin & Muharam, 2021).

Macroeconomic theory was born from a book written by JM Keynes entitled " the general theory of employment, interest and money " in 1937. Keynes was an economist at the University of Cambridge, England. The book is a milestone. The early history of western economic thought in Keynes's book shows that unemployment can occur and even for an indefinite period of time. Many economists accept Keynes's opinions and this group is called Keynesian economists and is currently used as a theory that is practiced and justified in many countries. The problems discussed in macroeconomics include problems related to the management and control of the economy in general. The task of macroeconomic economic control is to ensure that the economy can work and grow in a balanced manner, avoiding situations that can disturb the general balance (Digdowiseiso, 2016).

Bibliometrics is a technique used to analyze and measure scientific publications, including journals, books and conferences. Bibliometrics can be used to evaluate research performance and scientific developments in a field. Bibliometric

metrics can include number of publications, price index, impact factor, and number of citations (Dubyna et al., 2022). Bibliometrics can also be used to measure individual performance, such as measuring the number of publications and citations of a researcher. Bibliometrics can be used to assess the performance of research institutions and universities, as well as to compare research performance between countries. However, bibliometrics is not always an appropriate measure of research quality, as other factors such as originality and impact of the research must also be considered (Jena et al., 2012).

VOSviewer is software that can be used to display and analyze scientific publication data, such as journals, books and conferences. This software can help present publication data in visual form, such as a VOS (Viewer of Science) diagram that shows the relationship between keywords and collaboration between researchers. VOSviewer can also be used to analyze citation data and display information about the number of citations, impact factors, and price indices. This software can also be used to create bibliometric reports that show individual or institutional research performance (Nurul & Winoto, 2022). VOSviewer is freely available to use, and can be downloaded from the software's official website (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library Research study is a review of existing literature in a research field. The purpose of a Library Research is to identify and evaluate existing sources so that they can provide an overview of research that has been conducted previously and help determine the direction of further research. Library Researchs can also help identify gaps or deficiencies in research that has been conducted previously, so that it can become a basis for conducting more meaningful and useful research (El-Halaby et al., 2021). Library Researchs can be done by searching for and reading sources related to research topics, such as scientific journals, books, and conferences. Then, these sources can be grouped and analyzed to evaluate the contribution of each source to the research topic (Ivanova & Tarnopol'skii, 1994). Carrying out a Library Research provides many benefits for a researcher, including providing the opportunity to demonstrate closeness and understanding of the research topic to be conducted, developing the theoretical framework and research methodology that will be used, positioning oneself as an expert researcher who has the ability to conduct research and master each stage, and show the public the benefits of the research carried out and how the research can overcome gaps or provide solutions to problems (Cahyono et al., 2019).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is the influence of macroeconomic variables. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on the influence of macroeconomic variables.

The source of data collection comes from searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sinta, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key "Macroeconomics" within the entire year period (1997-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals that have been published collected the data; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics based on Library Research studies (Budianto, 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Emiliani et al., 2023).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications on the Influence of Macroeconomic Variables

The results of searching scientific publications regarding the influence of Macroeconomic variables during the period 1997 to 2022, show an increase in publications every year, especially in the last 5 years. In fact, in 2021, there will be 59 articles published. So, the average scientific publication regarding the influence of macroeconomic variables is as many as 19 articles per year. This increase in publications has occurred in parallel since 2012. This aims to increase the quality and quantity of research in higher education so as to increase its competitiveness globally.

Table 1. Journal publication data on macroeconomics by year

Name of					
Year	Amount	Year	Amount	Year	Amount
	Publication		Publication		Publication

1997	1	2007	6	2015	25
1998	1	2008	1	2016	39
1999	1	2009	8	2017	48
2001	1	2010	5	2018	46
2002	1	2011	7	2019	37
2003	3	2012	13	2020	54
2004	1	2013	23	2021	59
2005	6	2014	19	2022	33
2006	3				
Total 441					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 27 affiliates/institutions that publish the most journals regarding the influence of macroeconomic variables. The E-Journal of Economics and Business at Udayana University is the largest journal publishing institution that publishes results on the influence of Macroeconomic variables, with a total of 7 journal publications.

Table 2. Affiliation/Institution of Macroeconomics scientific journal publishers

	Amount Publication
Udayana Univ Economics and Business E-Journal	7

CALYPTRA: University of Surabaya Student Scientific Journal	6
Monetary Economics and Banking Bulletin	5
Journal of Business Administration, Management E-Journal	4
At-Tharadhi: Journal of Economic Studies, Al-Iqtishad: Journal of Economic Sciences Sharia, Journal of Administration and Business, PROFIT: Journal of Administration and Business, E-JRM: Electronic Journal of Research and Management, E-Journal Accounting, Ecosains: scientific journal of economics and development, UKUITAS: journal of economics and finance, INOVASI	3
Islamic Banking, Acquisition: Accounting Journal, An-Nisbah: Economic journal Sharia, Ekonis: Journal of Economics and Business, Eqien: Journal of Economics and Business, J-EBIS (journal of economics and business), ACCESS: Journal of Economics and Business, Journal of Management and Business, Bulletin of Economic Studies, e-Journal Scientific Accounting Research, Diponogoro Journal of Management, Fair Value: scientific journal of accounting and finance, Iqtishoduna, Economic journal of emerging markets	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

The most productive researchers are: R. Adisetiawan from Batanghari University, Faculty of Economics, Fitri Rahmawati and Nirmala Baini from Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University, Yogyakarta, who wrote 2 articles.

Mapping Bibliometric Studies around the Influence of Macroeconomic Variables

Search results on research articles on the Garuda Website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information System) format, input and analyzed with VOSviewer. Then we get the results of the network visualization of the development co-word map research regarding the influence of Macroeconomic variables into 5 clusters and 139 items, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding the influence of macroeconomic variables. Data processed, VOSViewer 1.6.17 software.

- Cluster 1, red is formed from 38 items, namely: Capita, CPI, data analysis, ecm, economic growth, economy, errpr correction model, exchange rate, export, foreign debt, foreign exchange reserve, government, growth, Indonesia, inflation, interest rate, investment, labor, level, long run, long term, macroeconomic indicator, macro economic variable, money, money supply, negative effect, positive effect, poverty, rate, region, relationship, short term, significant negative effect, significant positive effect, trade, var, vector error correction model, yield.
- Cluster 2, green is formed from 36 items, namely: bei, bi rate, interest, Indonesian stock exchange, capital market, composite stock price index, dollar, economy, exchange rates, f test, world oil prices, ihsg, stock price index composite, inflation, issi, jakarta islamic index, jci, jii, kur, exchange rate, multiple linear regression, multiple linear regression, nikkei, exchange rate, GDP, rupiah, rupiah exchange rate, joint stock, sbi, sbi interest rate, stock price index, interest rates, t test, macroeconomic variables, world oil price.
- Cluster 3, blue is formed from 33 items, namely: asset, company, current ratio, debt, der, earnings, eps, equity, equity ratio, financial performance, firm value, food, fundamental factor, Indonesian stock exchange, Indonesian stock exchange, inflation rate, investor, Islamic stock, macroeconomic factor, net profit margin, per, company, population, price earning ratio, purposive sampling, purposive sampling method, return, roe, significant effect, stock, stock price, stock return, systematic risk.
- Cluster 4, yellow is formed from 21 items, namely: bank, bopo bps, car, deposit ratio, fdr, financing, gdp, gross domestic product, Islamic banking, ldr, loan, macro economic variables, macroeconomic conditions, npf, npl, performance, performing loan, roa, role.
- Cluster 5, purple consists of 11 items, namely: firm, idx, influence, investment decision, investment decision, Islamic mutual fund, macro economy, macroeconomic, profitability, risk, significant influence, value.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors that Influence Macroeconomic Variables

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, researchers found 52 factors that influence Macroeconomic variables, that is:

(1) Actualization of Islamic monetary policy. The actualization of good Islamic monetary policy can influence economic growth and inflation. A good Islamic monetary policy can ensure that the money supply is not too much, thereby reducing the risk of inflation. On the other hand, good monetary policy can increase capital availability and liquidity in financial markets, thereby increasing investment and economic growth.

(2) Inflation rate. The inflation rate can affect economic growth and employment. High inflation can cause higher costs of living and a decrease in people's purchasing power, which can reduce consumption and economic growth. Additionally, high inflation can also cause companies to raise the prices of their products, which can lead to unemployment and lower investment levels.

(3) Economic growth. Economic growth can affect employment levels and inflation. Good economic growth can increase employment levels and reduce inflation. However, economic growth that is too fast can cause inflation and a trade balance deficit.

(4) Employment. Employment can affect inflation rates and economic growth. A high unemployment rate can cause consumption and economic growth to decline, while a low unemployment rate can increase inflation because it increases demand and labor costs.

(5) Change in discount rate. Changes in discount rates can affect economic growth, inflation and interest rates. An increase in the discount rate can reduce consumer demand and investment, which can reduce economic growth. However, an increase in the discount rate can also reduce inflation and interest rates, thereby reducing inflation risk and encouraging investment.

(6) The growth rate of the money supply. Growth in the money supply affects inflation and interest rates. If the money supply increases faster than economic growth, it will cause inflation. An increase in inflation will cause interest rates to rise, which in turn can hamper economic growth.

(7) Changes in the unemployment rate. A high unemployment rate can indicate a weak economy, as companies tend to reduce production and cut costs when demand declines. This may also lead to a decrease in consumer spending. On the other hand, a low unemployment rate could lead to rising wages and consumer demand, which could revive economic growth.

(8) Consumer Price Index/CPI growth rate. CPI measures changes in the prices of goods and services purchased by consumers. If the CPI rises quickly, it can indicate inflation, which can affect interest rates and economic growth. If the CPI rises too quickly, then consumers may buy fewer goods and services, which in turn could lead to a decline in production and economic growth.

(9) Industrial production. Industrial production can reflect the health of the economy, because industrial production requires human and material resources. If industrial production increases, it can indicate healthy economic growth. On the other hand, a decline in industrial production can be a sign of an economic slowdown.

(10) Percentage change in the Yen-Dollar exchange rate. Changes in exchange rates between two currencies can affect trade and economic growth. If the yen strengthens against the dollar, then Japanese goods will become more expensive for American buyers, which could reduce Japanese exports to America and in turn affect Japan's economic growth. On the other hand, if the dollar strengthens against the yen, then American goods will become more expensive for Japanese buyers, which could reduce American exports to Japan.

(11) Percentage change in oil prices. Percentage changes in oil prices can have a major impact on the global and domestic economy because oil is the primary fuel used in production and transportation. An increase in oil prices can cause inflation because production costs rise and the prices of goods and services related to oil will rise. This can also reduce consumer purchasing power and damage economic growth.

(12) Financing the budget deficit. Budget deficit financing, if done excessively, can create a heavy debt burden on the government and reduce investor confidence in a country's economy. This can cause a decrease in the country's currency exchange rate, inflation, and economic instability.

(13) Total trades. Total trade can affect a country's economic growth. If total trade increases, this can increase production and exports, thereby opening up opportunities for economic growth. Conversely, if total trade decreases, this can reduce demand for goods and services, thereby reducing production and affecting economic growth.

(14) The role of business incubators. The role of business incubators can help accelerate business and economic growth. Business incubators can provide financial support, mentorship, and facilities to start a business. If more business incubators were available, this could increase the number and success of startups, which could help spur economic growth.

(15) Sharia Mutual Funds. Sharia mutual funds are investment instruments that follow sharia principles. Investments in Sharia mutual funds do not involve interest, speculation, or industries that are considered haram in Islam. Sharia mutual funds can provide an investment alternative for people who want to invest in accordance with their principles. On a large scale, increased investment in Sharia mutual funds can help develop the Sharia-based financial sector, and contribute more to overall economic growth.

(16) Rise in fuel prices. An increase in fuel prices can have an impact on increasing prices of goods and services in general. This is because increasing transportation costs can affect the costs of producing and distributing goods and services. Rising fuel prices can also affect inflation, consumer spending and economic growth.

(17) Interest rate policy. Interest rate policies can affect people's investment and savings levels. A low interest rate policy can encourage investment and reduce savings, which results in higher economic growth. Conversely, high interest rate policies can encourage savings and reduce investment, which can slow economic growth.

(18) Food price policy. Food price policies can affect inflation and consumer purchasing power. If food prices rise, the prices of goods and services also tend to rise, which has an impact on inflation. Apart from that, rising food prices can also affect consumer purchasing power because consumers have to spend more money to buy basic necessities.

(19) Monetary policy. Monetary policy can affect the supply of money and credit in the market, which impacts inflation and interest rates. Tight monetary policy can tighten the supply of money and credit, which can reduce inflation but can slow economic growth. Conversely, loose monetary policy can increase inflation but can encourage economic growth.

(20) Fiscal policy. Fiscal policy includes government spending and tax policy. Expansionary fiscal policy, namely increasing government spending or reducing taxes, can encourage economic growth. However, fiscal policy that is too expansive can cause budget deficits and inflation. Conversely, tight fiscal policy can reduce inflation and reduce the budget deficit, but it can slow economic growth.

(21) returns. Stock return is the return on investment that investors get from owning shares in the company. The influence of stock returns on macroeconomics depends on how much investment investors make in the stock market. If investors buy shares in large quantities, the resulting share returns can have a positive impact on economic growth.

(22) Sectoral risks. Sectoral risk is related to economic conditions in a particular sector, for example the banking, agricultural or manufacturing sectors. If sectoral risks are large enough, then this can have a negative impact on overall economic growth, especially if the sector has an important role in the economy.

(23) Regional economic policy. Regional economic policy includes policies implemented by local governments to promote economic growth in a particular region. If this policy is successfully implemented well, it can help increase overall economic growth.

(24) Sharia share prices. Sharia share price refers to the share price of a company that complies with Sharia principles in its operations. If Sharia share prices rise, this can indicate investor confidence in the company and its performance, which in turn can have a positive impact on economic growth.

(25) National savings. National savings reflects the amount of money held by citizens in banks, investment instruments, and other financial products. Large amounts of national savings can provide a source of funds for investment, which can help encourage economic growth. However, if national savings are too high, this can also have a negative impact on economic growth, as it encourages less consumer spending.

(26) Value Added Tax/VAT. VAT can affect the economy through its influence on the prices of goods and services. If VAT is increased, the prices of goods and services will rise, which has the potential to reduce people's purchasing power and reduce demand. On the other hand, if VAT is reduced, the prices of goods and services will become cheaper, thereby increasing people's purchasing power and encouraging demand.

(27) Trade liberalization. Trade liberalization can affect the economy through increasing market access and global competition. By reducing trade barriers, such as tariffs and import quotas, countries can increase market access for domestic producers to global markets and vice versa. However, tougher global competition can force domestic manufacturers to improve the efficiency and quality of their products to remain competitive.

(28) Third Party Funds/DPK. DPK can influence the economy through its influence on liquidity and interest rates. If banks have more deposits, they can provide more loans, thereby increasing liquidity and potential economic growth. On the other hand, if deposits decrease, banks may raise interest rates to attract more deposits, which could slow economic growth.

(29) Foreign debt. Foreign debt can affect the economy through its influence on the balance of payments and currency exchange rates. If a country is too dependent on foreign debt, then the country can experience problems paying its debt and affect the exchange rate of its currency. However, foreign debt can also help finance investment in development projects that can increase economic growth.

(30) Fiscal sustainability. Fiscal sustainability, namely the balance between state income and expenditure in the long term, can influence the economy through its influence on investor confidence and economic stability. If the fiscal is sustainable, then investors will have more confidence in the country's economic policies and the potential for sustainable economic growth. However, if the fiscal is not sustainable, then investors may lose confidence and trigger economic instability.

(31) Risk of banking credit going public. Credit risk of banks going public refers to the possibility of default on loans by borrowers from banks that have gone public. If credit risk increases, this can have a negative impact on the stability of the banking system, which in turn can affect overall economic growth.

(32) Perception of corruption. Perception of corruption refers to the public's view of the level of corruption in government. If the perception of corruption is high, this can lead to a decrease in public trust in the government and other public institutions, which in turn can have a negative impact on economic growth.

(33) Composite Stock Price Index/IHSG. IHSG reflects the performance of the stock market in Indonesia. If the JCI rises, this can show that investment in the stock market is increasingly promising, so it can encourage economic growth. However, if the JCI falls, this could indicate uncertainty in the stock market and have a negative impact on economic growth.

(34) National income. National income refers to the income generated by all citizens in a country within a certain period of time. If national income increases, this can encourage economic growth, because consumption and investment will increase. However, if national income falls, this can reduce people's purchasing power and reduce economic growth.

(35) Household consumption behavior. Household consumption behavior reflects people's shopping patterns. If people tend to reduce spending, then this can show a lack of confidence in the economy, which can have a negative impact on economic growth. However, if people tend to increase spending, this can strengthen economic growth through consumption and investment.

(36) Fluctuations in the share price index for the property and real estate sector services industry. Stock price fluctuations can affect investor confidence and market sentiment towards the property and real estate sector. An increase in share prices can increase confidence and investment in the sector, while a decline in share prices can trigger a decrease in investment and reduced economic activity in the sector.

(37) Analysis of trading volume in state-owned/state-owned banking shares. The trading volume of state-owned/state-owned banking shares can reflect investor confidence in banking and economic performance as a whole. High stock trading volume can indicate strong investor confidence, while low trading volume can indicate investor concern and market uncertainty.

(38) The impact of the sub prime mortgage crisis. The sub prime mortgage crisis that occurred in 2008 triggered a global recession and affected various economic sectors. The crisis triggered a decline in asset prices, increased unemployment, and reduced consumer and investor confidence. The long-term impacts of the crisis include reduced economic growth and changes to global financial regulations.

(39) Motor vehicle tax and title transfer fees. Motor vehicle taxes and transfer fees can influence consumers' decisions to purchase motor vehicles and can provide income to the government. An increase in motor vehicle taxes can reduce consumer demand and spending, while a reduction in motor vehicle taxes can increase consumer demand and spending.

(40) King Salman Investments. King Salman's investments can have a positive impact on the economy through increasing foreign investment and growth in certain sectors. The investment could increase employment and consumer spending, as well as strengthen economic ties between the two countries. However, the impact may vary depending on the sector invested in and the use of the investment.

(41) Fiscal balance. Fiscal balance refers to a situation where government revenues equal government expenditure. If fiscal balance is maintained, then economic stability can be maintained. If revenues are greater than expenditures, then the budget surplus can be used to pay debts or increase government spending which can trigger economic growth. On the other hand, if expenditure is greater than revenue, then a budget deficit occurs and the government must find a way to finance this expenditure, which can cause an increase in debt and inflation.

(42) Number of Indonesian Workers/TKI. The number of Indonesian Migrant Workers (TKI) working abroad can have an impact on the Indonesian economy. If migrant workers send most of their income to Indonesia, this can increase foreign exchange and ease pressure on the trade balance. However, if many migrant workers return to Indonesia and do not have jobs, this could increase the burden of unemployment and reduce domestic consumption.

(43) Investment, consumption, saving, government spending. Investment, consumption, saving, and government spending are important factors that can influence economic growth. Investment can encourage economic growth by building infrastructure, increasing production and creating jobs. Consumption can strengthen the economy by increasing demand and driving production. Savings can help finance

investment and government spending. Government spending can also help build infrastructure and strengthen the public sector.

(44) Increase in foreign debt. The increase in foreign debt could become a burden on the Indonesian economy if it is not balanced with sufficient economic growth. If there is too much foreign debt, the interest that must be paid every year can drain the government budget and weaken the rupiah. However, if foreign debt is used for productive investment and produces sufficient economic growth, then the debt can provide long-term benefits.

(45) Inflation. Inflation can affect people's purchasing power and overall economic stability. If inflation is too high, the prices of goods and services will rise and money will lose its value. This can reduce consumption and reduce economic growth. However, a little inflation (between 2-3%) can help increase economic growth by encouraging consumption and investment.

(46) Gross Domestic Product/GDP. GDP is an important indicator in determining the economic health of a country. The higher the GDP, the greater the economic contribution to society's welfare. High GDP can increase people's purchasing power, investment, and demand for goods and services, which in turn can spur economic growth.

(47) Interest rate. Interest rates affect economic activity broadly, primarily through their influence on investment and consumption. Low interest rates can encourage credit and borrowing, which in turn can increase investment and consumption. Meanwhile, high interest rates can reduce loans and investment, thereby reducing economic activity.

(48) Currency exchange rate. Currency exchange rates can affect a country's exports and imports. A low exchange rate can increase exports and reduce imports, which in turn can increase GDP. On the other hand, a high exchange rate can reduce exports and increase imports, thereby reducing GDP.

(49) Foreign debt. Foreign debt can affect a country's economic stability. High debt can increase the risk of inability to pay debts, and can trigger a decline in investor confidence. However, moderate foreign debt can increase investment and economic growth.

(50) Sharia Bank core capital. Sharia Bank core capital can influence the bank's ability to channel funds to the public and business actors. Sufficient capital can increase public trust in banks and increase the bank's ability to provide credit and loans.

(51) Sharia Mutual Funds. Sharia mutual funds can be an attractive investment option for people who want to invest in accordance with sharia principles. On a large scale, Islamic mutual funds can help increase investment funds available in the capital market, which in turn can spur economic activity.

(52) Population aging. Population aging can affect a country's economic health, particularly through its effects on labor and consumption. Population aging can reduce labor productivity and consumer demand, which in turn can reduce economic growth. However, population aging can also increase demand for products and services related to health and wellness, thereby fueling the growth of certain sectors.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research on the Influences Caused by Macroeconomic Variables

Library Research study in research journals that have been downloaded, researchers found 117 influences caused by macroeconomic variables, that is: (1) Stock market; (2) Middle income trap; (3) Poverty and unemployment levels; (4) Yield on Government Debt Securities (SUN); (5) Stability of Sharia and Conventional banks; (6) Halal industry; (7) Stock returns; (8) Foreign direct investment; (9) Composite Stock Price Index/IHSG; (10) Index Indonesian Sharia Shares (ISSI); (11) Bad credit; (12) Company abnormal returns; (13) Financial performance; (14) Share price; (15) Number of children; (16) Intrinsic value of shares; (17) Low economic growth; (18) Inflation; (19) Credit growth; (20) Low exchange rate; (21) Energy crisis; (22) APBN

deficit; (23) Imbalance in the balance of trade and payments; (24) Exchange rate movements; (25) Money market deregulation; (26) Globalization; (27) Export, import and consumption; (28) Economic growth; (29) Investment; (30) National economic patterns; (31) Impact of free trade arrangements; (32) Portfolio return; (33) Stock portfolio; (34) Corporate bond yield; (35) Underpricing on company; (36) Interdependence of dividend policy; (37) Sharia exchange; (38) Jakarta Islamic Index/JII; (39) LQ45 share price; (40) Efficiency of the Sharia banking industry; (41) Collection of funds at commercial banks; (42) Value of manufacturing companies on the stock exchange; (43) Firm value; (44) Aggregate demand; (45) Capital Structure (Capital Structure); (46) Stock Beta Sharia; (47) Trade balance; (48) Farmer's exchange rate; (49) Level of underpricing during initial public offering; (50) Gross Regional Domestic Product/GRDP.

Next: (51) Management of the casualty insurance industry; (52) Foreign debt; (53) Foreign investment; (54) General credit distribution; (55) Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises/MSMEs; (56) Profitability of non-foreign exchange banks; (57) Sectoral stock price index; (58) Country currency; (59) Credit risk; (60) Indonesia's foreign exchange reserves; (61) Stock price index; (62) Leverage; (63) The value of the company; (64) Property and real estate sector share price index; (65) Returns on property and real estate shares; (66) Non Performing Financing/NPF; (67) Non Performing Loans/NPL; (68) Bank profitability; (69) Amount of zakat collected; (70) Price index property shares; (71) Financing through Third Party Funds/DPK; (72) Nikkei 225; (73) Indonesian Exports; (74) Currency redomination; (75) Rupiah exchange rate; (76) Financial sector; (77) Real sector; (78) Educated unemployed; (79) Poverty; (80) Profitability of sharia banking; (81) Third Party Funds/Sharia Banking DPK; (82) Growth in non-oil and gas income tax revenues; (83) Request for Sharia banking Murabahah financing; (84) Sharia life insurance investment results; (85) Net Asset Value/NAV of Sharia Mutual Funds; (86) Productive credit growth; (87) Indonesian cocoa bean exports; (88) Financing problems at Sharia Banks; (89) Prediction of share price volatility of industrial and beverage sub-sector companies; (90) Performance of the West Java and Banten Regional Development Bank; (91) Liquid stock market; (92) Productive and consumptive financing in Sharia Banking; (93) Development of Sharia Banking assets; (94) Growth of credit unions in Southeast Asia; (95) Return On Assets/ROA Sharia Banking; (96) Foreign direct investment between China and Indonesia; (97) Non-oil and gas exports; (98) Beta of shares in the mining industry; (99) Good Financial Governance; (100) Property company share price.

Next: (101) Capital markets; (102) Banking share prices; (103) Yield spreads of East Asian countries; (104) Indonesian Trade; (105) Debt interest sensitivity; (106) CSR Disclosure; (107) Export volume of coconut oil commodities; (108) Stock price volatility; (109) Growth of the property industry; (110) Sharia Banking market share; (111) Conditions of financial difficulties for manufacturing issuers on the Stock Exchange; (112) Primary balance; (113) Land comprehensive income and comprehensive income persistence; (114) Financial distress; (115) Performance of stock mutual funds; (116) Number of zakat receipts at Baznas; (117) Buyer decisions in E-Commerce.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: The number of research publications regarding the influence of Macroeconomic variables during the period from 1997 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 441 research articles, which come from international journals indexed by Scopus, international journals and national journals indexed by Sinta. Affiliates/institutions The most published research results is the E-Journal of Economics and Business at Udayana University, with a total of 7 journal publications. The researchers who were most productive in publishing research results were R. Adisetiawan from Batanghari University, Faculty of

Economics, Fitri Rahmawati and Nirmala Baini from Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University, Yogyakarta, who wrote 2 articles. In mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding the influence of Macroeconomic variables are divided into 5 clusters and 139 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 38 topics, cluster 2 consists of 36 topics, cluster 3 consists of 33 topics, cluster 4 consists of 21 topics, and cluster 5 consists of 11 topics. Based on the Library Research, there are 2 main research themes regarding the influence of Macroeconomic variables, namely: (1) Factors that influence Macroeconomic variables, with a total of 52 factors; and (2) Influence caused by Macroeconomic variables, with a total of 117 influences.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Library Research Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya

- Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH*. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Library Research. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>

- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>

Future research will use a larger data sample to reveal a wider research scope, considering the limitations of the data sample used in this research. Apart from that, it is also important to involve a longer time span of research data in order to obtain the following research results :

(1) It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization; and (2) The results of the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex manner.

Bibliography

Budianto, EWH (2022a). Research Mapping Mudharabah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions: Vosviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. J-EBIS (Journal of Islamic Economics and Business), 7 (1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>

Budianto, EWH (2022b). Mapping Research Regarding Musyarakah Agreements in Sharia Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. JESI (Journal of Indonesian Sharia Economics), 12 (1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)

Budianto, EWH (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING OF REPUTATION RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING: VOSVIEWER BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY AND LIBRARY RESEARCH. Al-Masraf: Journal of Financial Institutions and Banking, Vol 8, No 1 (2023): January - June 2023, 94–113. <https://doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>

Budianto, EWH, & Dewi, NDT (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. Maliki Islamic Economics Journal (M-IEC Journal), 2 (December), 76–94.

Budianto, EWH, & Dewi, NDT (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING OF DIVIDEND PER SHARE (DPS) RATIO IN SHARIA AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING: VOSVIEWER BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY AND LIBRARY RESEARCH. Al-Mal: Journal of Islamic Accounting and Finance, 04 (01), 109–126. <https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

Budianto, EWH, Dewi, NDT, & Abidin, UA (2023). Mapping Research on Third Party Fund Ratios (DPK) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: Vosviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking, 7 (1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>

Budianto, EWH, Saputra, HMGA, & Dewi, NDT (2023). Mapping Research Topics Regarding Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS): VOS viewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. EL MUDHORIB: Journal of Islamic Economics and Banking Studies, 3 (2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>

Cahyono, EA, Sutomo, & Harsono, A. (2019). Library Research: A Guide to Writing and Organizing. Journal of Nursing, 12.

Digdowniseiso, K. (2016). Macro economics. In Unesa University Press.

Dubyna, M., Popelo, O., Kholiavko, N., Zhavoronok, A., Fedyshyn, M., & Yakushko, I. (2022). Mapping the Literature on Financial Behavior: a Bibliometric Analysis Using the VOSviewer Program. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 19, 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2022.19.22>

El-Halaby, S., Aboul-Dahab, S., & Bin Qoud, N. (2021). A systematic Library Research on AAOIFI standards. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 19 (2), 133–183. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-06-2020-0170>

Emiliani, E., Budianto, EWH, & Dewi, NDT (2023). Mapping Research Topics around Hawalah Agreement on Sharia Financial Inclusion: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and

Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286692>

Gozali, M., Saputra, MA, Dewi, NDT, & Budianto, EWH (2023). Research Mapping Regarding Determinant Variables of Return on Equity (Roe) in Sharia Banking: Vosviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. *IDEI: Journal of Economics & Business*, 4 (1), 34– 47. <https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>

Ivanova, A.N., & Tarnopol'skii, B.L. (1994). Effects of diffusion instability in inhomogeneous conditions. *Computational Mathematics and Mathematical Physics*, 34 (8–9), 1045–1055. Jena, K. L., Swain, D. K., & Sahu, S. B. (2012). Scholarly communication of the electronic

libraries from 2003-2009: A bibliometric study. *Electronic Libraries*, 30 (1), 103–119. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02640471211204097>

Nurul, F., & Winoto, Y. (2022). Bibliometric mapping of research developments using information architecture topics on Google scholar using Vosviewer Bibliometric mapping of research developments using information architecture topics on Google scholar using Vosviewer Abstra. ... of Libraries and Information ..., 2 (1), 43–60.

Priyono, & Candra, T. (2016). The Essentials of Macroeconomics. In *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*.

Putra, SSMMFH (2021). Analysis of the Influence of Macroeconomics and World Stock Indexes on the Composite Stock Price Index (IHSG). *Syntax Idea*, Vol 3 No 7 (2021): Syntax Idea, 1598–1611.

Rofika, H., Budianto, EWH, & Dewi, NDT (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING AROUND SHARIA AND CONVENTIONAL MAYBANK: VOSVIEWER BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY AND LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Economic Journal: Journal of Economics*, 14 (1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>

van Eck NJ, W.L. (2022). VOSviewer Manual Version 2.6.18. In Leiden: Univeristeit Leiden.

Leiden: Univeristeit Leiden.

Jasmine, Amanda Ratri, & Muharam, H. (2021). analysis of the influence of corporate governance, financial, indicators and macro-economic factors on financial distress. 6 (12), 6.

ZAHARA, V. M., & ANWAR, C. J. (2020). MICROECONOMICS (AN INTRODUCTION). CV.

INDONESIAN SCIENCE MEDIA.